

Meta-Cognitive Awareness and Socialization as Predictors of Teachers' Professionalism

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Abstract:- This research ascertained the significant influence of meta cognitive awareness and socialization on the teachers' professionalism. Then on-experimental quantitative design - utilizing descriptive-correlational technique was used. The study conducted at Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental. There were 300 public teachers as respondents and were gathered through stratified random sampling. In gathering the data, survey questionnaires on meta-cognitive awareness, socialization, and professionalism were used as research instruments. The mean, Pearson r, and regression analysis were used as the statistical tools in this research. The study discovered that meta cognitive awareness was resulted at a high level, and socialization was resulted at a very high level; on the other hand, teacher professionalism was resulted at a high level. Using Pearson r, the results revealed that there was positive significant correlation between metacognitive awareness and professionalism; and, there was positive significant correlation between socialization and professionalism. Further, the regression analysis showed data that metacognitive awareness had significant influence on the professionalism of teacher. Moreover, the data also showed that socialization had no significant influence on the professionalism of public-school teachers.

Keywords:- Educational management, meta-cognitive awareness, socialization, professionalism, regression, public-teachers, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers contribute a significant responsibility in the educational sphere, since their presence physically, emotionally, spiritually, and academically could highly influence learners (Galeshi&Taimoory, 2019). Along with their profession, they need to internalize within them the essence of professionalism, such as internalizing the professional code of conduct, being competent in teaching, and being able to apply the positive views in their work and workplace (Feeney & Freeman, 2018; Darling-Hammond 2017). However, in reality, it is not easy to handle the conversion of knowledge from educational theories taught in school to real actual situation in the educational field (Spătărelu, 2019). The transition process could be a source of stress, pressures and even shock in the workplace (Powell & Bodur, 2019). Additionally, these are also among the reasons why teachers lose their motivation and decided to quit in their career and shift to another profession (Chong & Lu, 2019).

It is very important to apply professionalism in the field of education. Learners' knowledge first draw attention to learning in the school (Cheng & Huang, 2018). Therefore, if teachers act without professionalism, such as coming to school late, displaying negative behavior, lacking of emotional teacher-student attachment, and incompetent in curricular school related duties and responsibilities, may not just impedes the effective student's learning and teacher's teaching. But also, it has a huge impact in school-related management (Makau, 2020; Yin, Huang, & Chen, 2019). These only shows to the educational environment that teachers failed to have an excellent performance and at the same time affect the students' performance academically (Makau, 2020).

Understanding the value of research on professionalism, the researcher has conducted a thorough literature study to identify potential contributing factors. Teachers in particular need to possess the knowledge (metacognitive awareness), dispositions (socialization), as well as the behaviors, attitudes, and qualities (professionalism) necessary to start a profession in teaching and complete the tasks in all the situation they come across (Vermunt, Vrikki, Warwick, & Mercer, 2017; Odike&Nnaekwe, 2018). In other words, teacher's metacognitive awareness is regarded as the first relevant variable. It is crucial for learning to be successful (Akben, 2020), productive instruction (Bagci &Unveren, 2020) and is necessary to advancing an educator's career (Backfisch, Lachner, Hische, Loose, & Scheiter, 2020). In this connection, the researcher found that socialization is also a significant variable. It is an effort that denotes the procedures for demonstrating that something has been done or accomplished to achieve higher standards of performance or quality (Salisu, Nayeri, Yakubu, & Ebrahimpour, 2019).

It should be mentioned that issues related to teacher professionalism are becoming more increasingly prevalent in various parts of the world (Boniface &Ngalawa, 2021). But there still lacks an investigation concerning variables like socialization and metacognitive awareness as characteristics that indicate professionalism. Despite this, teachers' metacognitive awareness offers a more effective means of understanding the goal of education (Haddad, Tabieh, Alsmadi, Mansour, & Al-Shalabi, 2022). Teachers must learn to socialize, which includes watching other instructors teach, getting feedback from their peers, building collegial relationships, and taking part in situations that promote lifelong learning (Salisu, et al., 2019). Therefore, the researcher wants to determine if socialization and metacognitive awareness aid in teachers' professional development. In the aforementioned setting, the researcher became interested in investigating if metacognitive

awareness and socialization are predictive of teacher's professionalism. As a result, this study represents an era of current knowledge with particular significance to the discipline of education.

Furthermore, the most important objective of the research is to ascertain whether metacognitive awareness and socialization are qualities that indicate professionalism in public school teachers.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Metacognitive Awareness

"Thinking about knowing" is how metacognition is defined, and it was observed that this term is another word for "metacognitive awareness" (Üstünbaş, 2020). Another definition provided for it was thinking about thinking (Duman, 2018). Some characterized it as an individual's understanding of understanding (Muhali, Yuanita, & Ibrahim, 2019). According to a researcher, metacognition is "one's understanding of and perspective on one's own cognitive processes, as well as one's attempts to control those processes to improve memory and learning" (Riney, 2021). Thus, there are numerous experts who have defined metacognition in various ways (Sumarno, 2020).

Numerous research has shown that it is beneficial to comprehend the metacognitive awareness process during studying (Sumarno, 2020). According to Bursalı and Öz (2018), learning success was increased through metacognitive awareness. It was seen as a higher cognitive skill and involved the capacity to monitor and coordinate one's own cognitive processes (Özçakmak, Köroğlu, Korkmaz, & Bolat, 2021). In addition, it was selected as a catch-all phrase that includes concepts like thinking skills, learning to learn, and self-regulated learning (Nordin & Yunus, 2020). Further, metacognitive abilities are critical abilities that relate to assist other abilities, according to a variety of thinking skills. (Ahdhianto, Marsigit, Haryanto, & Santi, 2020). Thus, the development of metacognitive skills is important for all ages for a variety of reasons. (Bakkaloglu, 2019).

Apart from this, other research views the (1) knowledge of cognition and (2) the regulation of cognition as the basic elements/components of metacognition (Sugita, 2018).

The first indicator is knowledge of cognition. Metacognitive knowledge or knowledge of cognition refers one's knowledge of his/her own learning (Asy'ari & Ikhsan, 2019; Tachie, 2019). It also refers to the extent to which learners learn using their own recollections and instructional strategies (Campano, 2019; Mancinetti, Guttormsen, & Berendonk, 2019). Additionally, it mentioned their cognitions or their overall understanding of cognition (Cole & Packer, 2019). Knowledge of cognition has three subcomponents namely: declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge and conditional knowledge (Stephanou & Mpiontini, 2017).

To begin with, declarative knowledge describes an individual's understanding of their cognitive methods, skills, and talents. (Kallio et al., 2017). Declarative knowledge allows one to understand both what they know and don't know, as well as how their own and others' learning is impacted. Also, declaratively knowledgeable people are aware of tactics that can be applied to improve task completion performance. (Potgieter & Walt, 2022).

Secondly, procedural knowledge describes an individual's understanding of how to apply tactics and methods to boost productivity and complete cognitive tasks. (Kallio et al., 2018). When someone has procedural knowledge, they will finish jobs by following established procedures (Hughes, 2017). For instance, gathering notes, paying close attention for crucial information, discarding irrelevant material, employing mnemonic devices, condensing the key points, and routinely checking oneself (Norris, 2019; Masoodi, 2020).

Finally, conditional knowledge describes an individual's understanding of the appropriate times and reasons to apply techniques to complete tasks (Dogan & Cephe, 2018). A person with conditional knowledge understands when and why to utilize techniques to accomplish tasks and when to present ideas. When someone has conditional knowledge, they can justify the application of particular tactics and choose the best ones for the given situation (Potgieter et al., 2022).

The second and last indicator is the regulation of cognition. Regulation of cognition refers to the capacity to use cognitive knowledge wisely in order to achieve a specific cognitive goal. It is a type of cognitive process mental operation that governs and controls metacognitive knowledge (Sarwer & Govil, 2017). Regulation of cognition is a set of five subcomponent metacognitive tasks that aid in controlling our thought and learning processes. It includes planning, monitoring, organizing (information management), debugging, and evaluating (Asy'ari et al., 2019; Langdon, Botnaru, Wittenberg, Riggs, Mutchler, Syno, & Caciula, 2019).

For instance, the capacity to choose sensible tactics, establish objectives, and distribute resources is referred to as planning (Zhang, D. & Zhang, L., 2019). Planning is the application of planning techniques, goal-setting, and task-accomplishment resources by an individual. The information management sub-process is related to the organizing subcomponent (Mahdi, Nassar, & Almsafir, 2019). Organizing is the process of managing information using cognitive methods and processes (Liebowitz, 2019).

Besides, when there is cognitive dissonance, information management is the proactive activity of gathering, clarifying, condensing, and concentrating only on pertinent information (Valencia-Vallejo, López-Vargas & Sanabria-Rodríguez, 2019). In line to this, monitoring involves evaluating a person's strategy efficacy and cognitive function (Langdon et al., 2019). In order to evaluate their own efficacy while observing, teachers also evaluate pupils' thinking through both verbal and nonverbal feedback.

Then, debugging is the process of using techniques to find and fix mistakes and presumptions regarding tasks and tactics that have been put into practice. (Kuvac&Koc, 2019). And the post hoc analysis of performance and strategy efficacy is the subcomponent of evaluation (Franić & Drnovšek, 2019).

In addition, teachers' experiences with difficulties vary in complexity and duration, which suggests that they need to engage in metacognition to enhance their cognitive regulation and cognitive understanding (Khan & Rasheed, 2019). In the ever-changing educational landscape, educators who are unaware of their own cognitive capacities will find it challenging to adjust (Saleh, 2019; Plant, Barac, & Sarens, 2019). Previous studies have demonstrated a connection between teachers' metacognitive abilities and the efficacy of their instructional strategies (Zepeda, Hlutkowsky, Partika, & Nokes-Malach, 2019; Asy'ari et al., 2019).

Moreover, another essential component of learning is metacognitive awareness (Concina, 2019; Kosior, Wall, & Ferrero, 2019). Thus, improved learning capacity and the capacity to integrate professional development learning into classroom practices are attributes of teachers with higher levels of metacognitive awareness (Hughes & Partida, 2020; Chon & Shin, 2019).

B. Socialization

Attending any professional group are bound to end in socialization (Moradi, Mollazadeh, Jamshidi, Tayefeh, Zaker, & Karbasi, 2017). Through the process of socialization, people acquire the knowledge, abilities, beliefs, norms, as well as appropriate actions of the group they belong to (Shahr, Yazdani, & Afshar, 2019).

In addition to this, professional socialization is the process by which an individual gets admitted as a member of a professional society (Shahr et al., 2019). Likewise, creating a professional identity and becoming acquainted with the tasks in the workplace are the first steps in the process (Moradi et al., 2017). Also, it is the method that contributes to professional customs, principles, and perspectives. In addition, the common factor among the current definitions is the existence of one's own opinion, knowledge, and obligations as a member of a professional body (Tahmasbi, Mirzaiean, Bonyadi, & Mohammadi, 2017). Furthermore, it is an essential part of socialization all throughout life (Page, 2019).

In addition to this, teachers learn how to participate in and be members of their surroundings through the socialization process. They acquire up new values, like the belief that coworkers will get along, and develop new abilities, including teaching. As they hone their teaching techniques, they also learn new guidelines and working environments. In order to establish a professional identity, they therefore reconsider the field and absorb its values (Gökçe, 2020). Thus, being socialized is essential for academic success (Shahr et al, 2019). Socialization has three components; these are the (1) Organization socialization, (2) Group Socialization, and (3) Task Socialization (Farnese, Spagnoli, & Livi, 2022).

Organizational socialization is the first domain. Through this procedure, the hired employee gains information and abilities that the organization deems essential. In addition, a person must first complete the formal schooling component of the professional socialization process before deciding on a career. Consequently, professional socialization occurs before organizational socialization.

In like manner, when an individual selects an organization to work for, the process of organizational socialization begins. When a new employee first starts working for an organization, they attempt to overcome their anxiety and doubt by expanding their knowledge and challenging their own assumptions. However, in circumstances when an organization's field of work regularly contradicts with what people acquire in formal schooling, organizational socialization is observed to be more widespread for individual growth. Courses, master's programs, seminars, and peer observation are, in fact, a few instances of formal socializing (Lantz-Andersson, Lundin & Selwyn, 2018). In fact, organizational socialization requires accountability to a particular organization (Shahr et al., 2019).

Group socialization is the second domain. It was a phrase used in the teaching profession to characterize relationships between teacher groups. Group instruction provides "a ready stream of information rooted in the everyday interactions of teachers and best mastered through lengthy discussion among those who have shared the same expertise."

In fact, it is an essential strategy for career progression. Additionally, it is becoming more frequently acknowledged that for professional learning to be effective—especially when it comes to teacher participation—instructors must impart their knowledge and experience to others (Lantz-Andersson et al., 2018). Likewise, individuals who collaborate to achieve a shared goal are referred to as "communities".

Not with standing their variations, all of these initiatives, whether official or informal, conclude with "teaching professionals assembling for their professional growth objectives." (Vangrieken, Meredith, Packer, & Kyndt, 2017). In like manner, research on teacher groups has highlighted how important it is for members to share common values, have well-defined objectives, and have mutual respect and trust (Lantz-Andersson et al., 2018).

Task organization is the third and final domain. It focuses on the tasks that must be completed in order to fulfill objectives or reach performance benchmarks. A few topics of task management were also covered. Coordination of task-related activities is essential to task management. As a result, one could claim that individuals concentrate on completing tasks that are essential to achieving organizational goals. Its main strength was that all required job duties were completed on time. An additional advantage is that professionals ensure efficient time management. They are therefore able to delegate jobs and ensure that work is completed quickly and effectively (Rüzgar, 2018).

In addition, it's common for aspiring teachers in particular to be expected to collaborate well with others and possess the skills and knowledge necessary to support their students' collaborative learning. An individual's performance in group learning determines their academic performance (Vuopala, Näykki, Isohätälä, & Järvelä, 2019). In addition, Collaborative education has the potential to be a useful tool for training future teachers (Häkkinen, Järvelä, Mäkitalo-Siegl, Ahonen, Näykki, & Valtonen, 2017).

By that, concentrating on teachers' daily tasks and classroom environments, mentoring is a technique that promotes teachers' professional development and helps to end their estrangement from one another (Dzerviniks, 2017). Thus, mentored new instructors shown excellent organizational abilities and were more capable of meeting their responsibilities (Paula et al., 2018).

C. Professionalism

Over the years, an immense quantity of literature on professionalism has been written (Fitzgerald, 2020). The fact that professionalism lacks a precise definition contributes to the dilemma. That is why every person possesses a distinct idea of what constitutes professionalism (Browne, Wall, Batt, & Bennett, 2018).

In general, the norms of conduct and values that professionals uphold were referred to as professionalism (Parija & Adkoli, 2019). Also, the manner in which an obligation is viewed is included in the notion of professionalism (Çöplü&Kartın, 2019). It also included having professional attitude (Syahrir, Syazali, Masykur, Amrulloh, Sada, & Listiani, 2018). In line with this, Syazali (2016) said that professionalism is defined as a commitment to a professional concept. It can also mean being someone who observes professional behavior, being able to make moral decisions in a particular scenario, having a responsibility to the community, and learning from experience (Fitzgerald, 2020).

In particular, it was claimed that professional teachers are those with the fundamental skills and the ability to regulate their own performance of routine tasks (Habibi, Hartinah, Rofiqul, Syazali, Lestari, Abdurrahman, & Jauhariyah, 2019). And curriculum mastery, topic proficiency in each lesson, evaluation technique mastery, task dedication, and consistency in the most general sense are among the fundamental skills that educators need to have (Habibi et al., 2019). In addition, the teachers' concept, methodology, and code of conduct align with the instructional plan or subject matter they are teaching (Agustini&Suyatna, 2018).

Furthermore, to ensure the quality of education, the teacher—a crucial participant in the educational process—must carry out their duties effectively (Andriani, Kesumawati, & Kristiawan, 2018). Clearly, this indicates that educators' complete assignments or work in an ethical manner in terms of both quantity and quality (Sinambela, 2018). Also, teachers ought to take their duties meticulously, professionally, and genuinely instead of seeing them as a hobby (Kartini & Kristiawan, 2019).

Also, the study of Van Oeffelt, Ruijters, Hees, & Simons (2018) added that conserving up with academic and professional developments, assessing one's own work critically, supporting the field along with other professionals, and collaborating with other professionals are all aspects of professionalism. It is important to remember that active professionalism is required in the teaching profession (Sherpa, 2018). Thus, teachers' professionalism consists of three domains, which are the (1) teachers' code of conduct, (2) teachers' commitment, and (3) teachers' perception (Alkiviadou, 2019; Malik, Shahzad, Raziq, Khan, Yusaf, & Khan, 2019; Kusumaningrum, Sumarsono, & Gunawan, 2019).

The code of conduct is the first domain. Ethics are fundamental to the way that education is practiced worldwide (Shapira-Lishchinsky, 2020). A professional code of ethics is a collection of guidelines designed to help professionals perform their employment duties with sincerity, devotion, passion, sincerity, and authenticity (Sherpa, 2018). Indeed, its goal was to set guidelines for moral behavior expectations for professionals in educational institutions (Schwimmer & Maxwell, 2017).

Then, codes of ethics provide detailed guidelines for defining moral behavior and outline the values that must be respected (Bijani, Ghodsin, Fard, Shirazi, Sharif, & Tehranineshat 2017). It should be noted that professional ethics are necessary. However, the significance of moral education in the formation of teachers has waned (Walters, Heilbronn, & Daly, 2018). And for many schools, obtaining teachers with the necessary training in professional ethics is an uphill task (Sharma, 2020).

In particular, commonly, teachers act unprofessionally in the classroom by not preparing lesson plans, arriving late, not marking students' workbooks, not finishing school records like diaries, registrations, and student results, managing exams, obtaining money illegally from parents, taking unapproved paid study leaves, drinking, using drugs, and engaging in immoral behavior. Also, teachers who are in limited sociability with others, experienced the most stress, exhaustion, and frustration (Özdemir & Demir, 2017).

Even with an abundance of degrees, awards, medals, extra certificates, and subject-matter expertise, a lack of professional ethics among teachers is a problem at many colleges. In actuality, the professional code of ethics addresses the ideas and principles that the professional should preserve in order to promote a pleasant work environment. To perform their work with persistence and devotion, professionals should always be expanding their professional knowledge and skills.

So, teachers' conduct and character are greatly influenced by their professional code of ethics. It will support and guide the educators in providing engaging and successful instruction. The instructors' appropriate use of the teaching profession's code of ethics undoubtedly contributes to the development of the school and the growth of students (Sherpa, 2018).

Commitment is the second domain. The term "professional commitment" has multiple definitions (Shoaib & Khalid, 2017). A person's affective reactions to their field of work form a psychological link known as professional commitment (Jia, Hou, & Wang, 2020). Furthermore, it is considered a sign of job dedication when someone persists in pursuing their professional goals (Wickramasinghe, 2017).

The term "commitment" can be used to describe "devotion" or "dedication" to a work in its fullest definition (Rani, 2019). Signs of devotion to one's work include, but are not limited to, reading publications for professional growth, joining professional clubs, and not thinking about giving up on the work (Özgenel, 2019). A key factor in accomplishing educational objectives is the dedication of the teacher. A teacher's commitment, according to Duraisamy and Selvan (2020), is their core values or beliefs within the context of education. They see their dedication as an essential component in the advancement of education (Fiftyana & Sawitri, 2018).

The perception domain is the final and third one. "Perception" in the context of professionalism refers to the set of ideals that constitute the fundamental principles of humanism in professional work. For example, according to Daniel et al. (2020), terms like empathy, respect, compassion, honor, and integrity are related to perception.

Furthermore, it has long been acknowledged that perceptions are a component of cognition. It is described as "a credible and vital way to acquire understanding for educators that has a direct effect on the ways educators work and accumulates through continuous professional involvement" (Hostetler, 2017). According to some academics, perception can also relate to a person's conscious understanding of their own career as an instructor, which communicates their professional identity. Furthermore, this includes extremely sentimental components including beliefs, sentiments, attitudes, and orientations (Karaolis & Philippou, 2019).

Clearly, teacher competency is, without a doubt, the capacity of an educator to have a collection of knowledge, skills, beliefs, and attitudes that direct their performance and achievement of the learning outcomes. Furthermore, the way one thinks and acts to practice their profession effectively and ethically is a reflection of their performance as a teacher (Weng, Liu, & Chuang, 2019). Stated differently, they ought to possess the capacity to design a cutting-edge instructional framework and harbor a positive outlook on the teaching profession (Moreno-Guerrero et al., 2020).

Beyond this, it was important to understand what makes a teacher competent to ensure successful learning. The most important components of student learning were also the caliber of the instructor and the caliber of the curriculum. These served as the cornerstone of education and had a big influence on how well pupils performed academically (Mammadova, 2018). Thus, educators need to constantly enhance their instruction using a range of methods. Additionally, in order to be better prepared to address problems in the future, they must expand their

competence through training or ongoing education (Kulgemeyer & Riese, 2018).

D. Correlation Between Measures

Metacognition among teachers can enhance their efficacy as teachers while also improving their professional development. Furthermore, metacognitive awareness is a crucial step in the development and learning process (Jaleel, 2016). They must possess professional, field, and world knowledge in order to accomplish this (Avcam & Babanoglu, 2016). Additionally, a study claims that metacognitive awareness is a workable strategy for enhancing teacher instruction (Jaleel, 2016).

In the interim, metacognitive awareness enhances learning (Bulut, 2018). Educating teachers about metacognitive awareness is crucial. To put it another way, teachers need to be able to incorporate their own metacognition into their lesson plans (Ozturk, 2017). Additionally, Dogra's (2016) study found that teachers' regular duties aid in the development of their metacognitive awareness and skills. Additionally, the field, educators, and program development specialists stand to gain a great deal from knowing more about instructors' metacognitive awareness, according to the study (Bulut, 2018).

In addition, it is more common to view the creation and enhancement of teaching quality as a collaborative process rather than the sole responsibility of individual faculty members (Bell & Thomson, 2018; Wingrove, Hammersley-Fletcher, Clarke, & Chester, 2018). Peer coaching could therefore be a useful alternative approach for teachers' professional growth (Zhang, Liu, & Wang, 2017). Furthermore, giving and getting comments might serve as a springboard for introspection (Lichtenberger-Majzikne, & Fischer, 2017). Similarly, coaching and collaboration have made it possible to expand professional knowledge and enhance teaching methods (Lofthouse, 2019).

In order for a teacher to perform in their role as a professional, they must also be adept at socializing in the community. Teachers need to be extremely skilled and able to blend in with their surroundings in order to carry out their duties as members of an educational institution. Laws, regulations, a code of behavior, moral principles, and religious beliefs must all be upheld (Kusuma et al., 2018).

The aforementioned literature is relevant to the research's variables, namely metacognitive awareness, socialization, and professionalism. The study has a strong connection to the readings, papers, and findings that are provided. To sum it up, a great deal of assistance was provided by the mentioned works in revealing potential connections between metacognitive awareness, socialization, and professionalism. They would also provide support for the study's presentation, outcomes, and conclusions.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used a non-experimental quantitative design with the descriptive correlation research technique. Non-experimental research involves data collection without treatment introduction or modification (Chiang, 2017). In this study, neither the environment nor the factors were changed.

Descriptive-correlation research designs disclose relationships and circumstances that exist and do not exist, and they explain and interpret what is (Panda, 2022). Additionally, it is a fact-finding study that gave the researcher the opportunity to look at the traits, actions, and experiences of the research subjects (Yeoman, Nardi, Bowater, & Nguyen, 2017).

Since it evaluated the metacognitive awareness, socialization, and professionalism of Governor Generoso public school teachers, the study was descriptive in character. This study employed a correlational research design, examining the potential predictive association between metacognitive awareness and socialization as well as professionalism. Primary data was collected through a survey questionnaire.

Therefore, the purpose of the study was to look into a connection between socialization and professionalism, metacognitive awareness and professionalism, and impact of these connections on the teachers' professionalism. The mediation was established using medgraph.

This study was conducted in public schools in municipality of Governor Generoso, Mindanao. It is located in the province of Davao Oriental, roughly at 6° 39' 17" North, 126° 4' 19" East, as seen in Figure 2. The specific locale of this study is the nine public secondary schools and one elementary school in Governor Generoso.

The respondents for this research were identified from the 627 total population of teachers employed in the public schools in Governor Generoso's in the academic year 2021–2022. The sample respondents of the study were supposed to be 245 respondents. The researcher used the Slovin's formula to determine the number of samples selected in the study.

Nonetheless, the 300 Governor Generoso school teachers were approved as respondents by the researcher. Therefore, Chris (2020) suggests that while conducting research including more than 600 populations, 300 respondents is likewise the optimal quantity. Furthermore, as shown in the summary of respondent distribution, stratified random sampling was employed to create a sample frame (Kimmons, 2022).

Additionally, the researcher wants to learn more about the experiences teachers have had with plantilla items. Thus, the teachers who are in on-the-job training, volunteer teachers, non-teaching personnel of the institution, and students were not included, while elementary, junior high, and senior high school instructors were included. Since the study's focus was on public teachers who have had with plantilla items. Additionally, if individuals were uncomfortable with any of the study's questions, they were

free to withdraw from participating. The researcher gave their well-being and personal motives top priority.

There were three parts of questionnaires adapted from different authors that were modified by the researcher. The experts also evaluated the questionnaire construction with an overall total mean score of 4.34 and a descriptive interpretation of very good. With the assistance of knowledgeable validators, the questionnaire was created in a very detailed format to make it easy and comfortable for the respondents to answer each question and comprehend the purpose of the study.

The research questionnaire was divided into three parts. The first set was the independent variable, metacognitive awareness, which had a Cronbach's alpha of .977 greater than 0.70. It has two indicators, namely, knowledge about cognition and regulation of cognition. This was adapted from the study of Pintrich (2002) and modified by the researcher. The first indicator, knowledge of cognition had 16 items and comprised of three sub-indicators namely: declarative knowledge, seven items; procedural knowledge, four items; and conditional knowledge, five items. The second indicator, regulation of cognition had 27 items and comprised of five sub-indicators namely: planning, eight items; information management strategy, six items; monitoring, four items; debugging strategies, four items; and evaluation, five items.

The second set was the other independent variable, socialization, which had a Cronbach's alpha of .976 greater than 0.70. The instrument was adapted from the study of Haueter, Macan, and Winter (2003) and modified by the researcher. There were three indicators in this variable: the first indicator, organization socialization, was composed of 12 items; the second indicator, group socialization, was composed of 12 items; and the third indicator, task socialization, was composed of 11 items.

The third set was the dependent variable, professionalism, which had a Cronbach's alpha result of .889 greater than 0.70. It was adapted from the study of Nebukenya (2010) and modified by the researcher. There were three indicators on this variable: the first indicator, code of conduct, was composed of seven items; the second indicator, commitment, was composed of five items; and the third indicator, perception was composed of two items.

The research variables were measured using a five-point Likert scale. Hence, Vonglao (2017) claimed that the Likert scale asked respondents to either check a box or leave blanks in response to a lot of questions about a stimulus, attitude, or object. It was customary to use averages, or, more broadly, any arithmetic operation, to treat the number that was immediately acquired from a rating scale as a measurement.

The five orderable gradations of metacognitive awareness with their respective range of means and descriptions were as follows: a range of means around 4.20 – 5.00 with descriptive level as very high means that the mentioned item manifested at all times; range of means around 3.40 – 4.19 with descriptive level as high means that

the mentioned item is manifested most of the time; a range of means around 2.60 – 3.39 with descriptive level as moderate means that the mentioned item is manifested occasionally; a range of means around 1.80 – 2.59 with descriptive level as low means that the mentioned item is manifested in few instances; and a range of means around 1.00 – 1.79 with descriptive level as very low means that the mentioned item is not manifested at all.

In addition, the required information obtained through a methodical process. Initially, the researcher requested permission for conducting the study through a letter via email to the Davao Oriental Department of Education School Division Superintendent. Additionally, the researcher requested permission to conduct the survey among the teachers in each of the schools covered by this study by means of a letter submitted to the principals. In August 2022, the survey was approved and questionnaires distributed to the public secondary and elementary teachers in Governor Generoso. In order to provide respondents with questionnaires, the researcher personally visited several public secondary schools as well as elementary schools.

Further, one week after the distribution, the researcher personally collected the surveys to give the respondents ample opportunity to respond. Fortunately, all the distributed questionnaires were successfully retrieved. The completed results were checked and tallied. Finally, after all the results

had tallied, these were analyzed and interpreted based on the purpose of the study.

The following statistical tools were used for a more thorough interpretation and analysis of the data: regression analysis was used to determine whether metacognitive awareness and socialization influence teachers' professionalism; mean was used to determine the level of metacognitive awareness of public teachers, level of socialization, and level of professionalism to answer problems 1, 2, and 3; and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to determine if the relationship between metacognitive awareness, socialization, and teachers' professionalism is really significant.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data which was obtained from the study participants is presented in this section. Based on the results, the data collected on the professionalism, socialization, and metacognitive awareness of public teachers are interpreted. Level of metacognitive awareness of teachers; level of socialization of teachers; level of professionalism of teachers; significance of the relationship between metacognitive awareness and socialization; socialization and teacher professionalism; and significance of the influence of predictor variables on teacher professionalism are the order in which the information gathered and the topics discussed are arranged.

Table 1: Level of Metacognitive Awareness

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Knowledge of Cognition (Declarative Knowledge)	0.48	4.17	High
Knowledge of Cognition (Procedural Knowledge)	0.55	4.12	High
Knowledge of Cognition (Conditional Knowledge)	0.56	4.14	High
Regulation of Cognition (Planning)	0.52	4.17	High
Regulation of Cognition (Information Management Strategy)	0.54	4.16	High
Regulation of Cognition (Monitoring)	0.55	4.13	High
Regulation of Cognition (Debugging Strategies)	0.64	4.17	High
Regulation of Cognition (Evaluation)	0.56	4.13	High
Overall	0.47	4.15	High

The level of metacognitive awareness had an overall SD of 0.47 with an overall mean score of 4.15 had the descriptive interpretation of high as presented in Table 1. This means that metacognitive awareness of teachers is manifested most of the time. This overall mean was the total result gathered from the mean scores of 4.17 or high for declarative knowledge, 4.12 or high for procedural knowledge, 4.14 or high for conditional knowledge, 4.17 or high for planning, 4.16 or high for information management strategy, 4.13 or high for monitoring, 4.17 or high for debugging strategies; and 4.13 or high for evaluation.

The indicators with the highest mean were declarative knowledge, planning and debugging strategies; followed by information management strategy, conditional knowledge, monitoring, evaluation; and procedural knowledge got the lowest mean. Thus, the high level of interpretation on the mean scores of each indicators exemplify that the public teachers reflected the statements in metacognitive awareness. This also means that the respondents manifested the items on metacognitive awareness most of the time.

Table 2: Level of Socialization

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Organization Socialization	0.54	4.22	Very High
Group Socialization	0.55	4.27	Very High
Task Socialization	0.52	4.34	Very High
Overall	0.51	4.28	Very High

The level of the metacognitive awareness of teachers was high. This means that metacognitive awareness most of the time influences the professionalism of the teachers. This also evident that the publicteachers exhibited the items specified in every indicator under metacognitive awareness. Thus, all of the indicators for metacognitive awareness were rated high in their mean scores.

This is congruent with the findings of Yildiz and Akdag (2018), that metacognitive awareness was helpful for teachers in teacher education programs in terms of both professional and personal development, and that it was a significant factor in increasing success, learning throughout the life span, creative and critical thinking, and building self-confidence.

The results of the study is also connected to the research by Virtanen, Niemi, and Nevgi (2018), in which educators stated a shared goal of advancing their professional development in order to strengthen their capacity to include metacognitive awareness into the curriculum. Furthermore, this result supports Zeng and Goh's (2018) conclusion that having a strong metacognitive awareness is beneficial for both teaching and learning.

In general, the two indicators and their metacognitive awareness subcomponents definitely affect profession or career, which affects the professionalism of instructors. This finding supports the findings of Karimi and Ziaabadi's (2019) study, which found that teachers' metacognitive awareness played a significant influence in classroom procedures, improving their instruction and getting students actively involved in learning.

The second objective was to ascertain the level of socialization, which had an overall SD of 0.51 with an overall mean score of 4.28 had a descriptive interpretation of very high as shown on Table 2. This means that socialization of teacher is evident at all times.

This overall mean was the total result gathered from the mean scores of: 4.22 or very high for organization socialization; 4.27 or very high for group socialization; and 4.34 or very high for task socialization.

The indicator with the highest mean was task socialization, followed by group socialization and task socialization got the lowest mean. Thus, the very high level of interpretation on the mean scores of each indicators shows that the items on socialization are all times observed by the public teachers. This also means that the items on socialization are observed by the respondents at all times.

The level of the nature of socialization extracted from the responses of public teachers, was very high. This means that the public teachers are informed toward organizational, group and task responsibilities. The result also signifies that the public teachers all times tend to display and exhibit the items specified in each indicator under socialization. Thus, all of the indicators were found very high in their mean score.

The study's findings are consistent with those of Salisu et al. (2019), who discovered that successful socialization processes to support the upholding and continuity of professional principles required good information transmission and practice. The same findings were reached by Swardt, Rensburg, and Oozthuizen (2018) study, which concluded that in order for professionals to improve consistently, their surroundings needed to assist them.

Table 3: Level of Professionalism

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Code of Conduct	0.56	4.25	Very High
Commitment	0.52	4.10	High
Perception	0.49	3.31	Moderate
Overall	0.39	3.89	High

The third objective was to measure the level of professionalism of public teachers, which had had an overall SD of 0.39 with the overall mean score of 3.89 had a descriptive interpretation of high as shown on Table 3. This means that professionalism of teachers is manifested or felt most of the time. This overall mean was the total result gathered from the mean scores of: 4.25 or very high for code of conduct; 4.10 or high for commitment; and 3.31 or moderate for perception.

The indicator with the highest mean was code of conduct, followed by commitment and perception got the lowest mean. Thus, the high level of interpretation on the mean scores of each indicators shows that the items on socialization are all times observed by the public teachers. This also means that the items on professionalism are perceived by the respondents most of the time.

The level of teacher professionalism was high. This means that the public teachers manifested most of the time in their profession. Furthermore, this implies that the public-secondary teachers most of the time display and exhibit the items specified in every indicator under professionalism. Thus, all indicators for professionalism are found high as the overall total in their mean scores.

Code of conduct was rated very high and ranked highest among the indicators or teacher's professionalism. This result is consistent with Sherpa's (2018) study, which found that professionals who followed certain guidelines intended to help them perform their jobs professionally created a favorable work atmosphere.

Further, the dedication, perspective, and self-control required of instructors in their area of work constitute their professionalism. It supports the statement made by Habibi, Hartinah, Umam, Syazali, Lestari, Abdurrahman, and

Jauharyah (2019) that teachers needed to develop a set of skills, such as mastery of the curriculum, subject matter of each lesson, methods of assessment, and strategies, commitment to work, and discipline in its broadest sense. Teachers play an important role because, as one information source states, they are real people who act as role models for their students (Abdurrahman, Saregar, & Umam, 2018). This is also consistent with the findings of the Syahrir et al. (2018) study, which showed that a teacher's professionalism was defined as their commitment to professional concepts and behaviors.

Conversely, a study by Armyanti, Mustika, and Soemantri (2020) found that teachers who demonstrated unprofessional traits in their work, such as poor time management, strained relationships with students, and a lack of a safe space for teachers and students to share feelings, were thought to have a significant impact on students' development as professionals and on their own professional performance and growth.

Shown in Table 4 are the results of the test on the significant relationship between the independent variable which is metacognitive awareness and dependent variable

which is teacher professionalism. Based on the Pearson's r test conducted among the indicators of the two variables, the overall correlation had a computed over-all r- value of 0.749 and a p-value less than 0.05; thus, there is significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and teacher professionalism. In addition to this, the result implies rejecting the null hypothesis.

Further, each indicator of the independent variable, metacognitive awareness when correlated with all the indicators of the dependent variable, professionalism obtained overall r- values ranging from 0.553 to 0.707. This means that there is also a strong positive correlation between metacognitive awareness and professionalism of public teachers.

Further, each indicator of the independent variable, metacognitive awareness when correlated with all the indicators of the dependent variable, professionalism obtained overall r- values ranging from 0.553 to 0.707. This means that there is also a strong positive correlation between metacognitive awareness and professionalism of public teachers.

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Metacognitive Awareness and Teacher Professionalism

Metacognitive Awareness	Teacher Professionalism			
	Code of Conduct	Commitment	Perception	Overall
Knowledge of Cognition (Declarative Knowledge)	.668* (0.000)	.551* (0.000)	.220* (0.000)	.663* (0.000)
Knowledge of Cognition (Procedural Knowledge)	.608* (0.000)	.558* (0.000)	.202* (0.000)	.630* (0.000)
Knowledge of Cognition (Conditional Knowledge)	.548* (0.000)	.470* (0.000)	.183* (0.001)	.553* (0.000)
Regulation of Cognition (Planning)	.726* (0.000)	.628* (0.000)	.175* (0.002)	.707* (0.000)
Regulation of Cognition (Information Management Strategy)	.585* (0.000)	.635* (0.000)	.230* (0.000)	.664* (0.000)
Regulation of Cognition (Monitoring)	.666* (0.000)	.619* (0.000)	.140* (0.015)	.659* (0.000)
Regulation of Cognition (Debugging Strategies)	.668* (0.000)	.596* (0.000)	.173* (0.002)	.662* (0.000)
Regulation of Cognition (Evaluation)	.598* (0.000)	.652* (0.000)	.119* (0.038)	.631* (0.000)
Overall	.734* (0.000)	.683* (0.000)	.209* (0.000)	.749* (0.000)

Metacognitive awareness found to have positive and significant correlation with the professionalism of public teachers. These results corroborate to the study of Kosior et al. (2019), which asserted that metacognitive awareness provided educators with a framework for instructing and assessing cognitive strategies. The outcomes are consistent with Ajayi's (2019) research, which showed that information was essential for learning effectively in any field.

The study's findings also bear with Shaukat and Chowdhury's (2021) assertion that teachers who are aware of professional standards are more likely to cultivate a dedication to teaching, high standards, and a favorable attitude toward their field.

Shown in Table 5 are the results of the test on the significant relationship between the independent variable which is socialization and dependent variable which is teacher professionalism. Based on the Pearson's r test conducted among the indicators of the two variables, the overall correlation had a computed over-all r- value of 0.597 and a p-value less than 0.05; thus, socialization and teacher professionalism are significantly correlated, and the outcome suggests rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Socialization and Teacher Professionalism

Socialization	Teacher Professionalism			Overall
	Code of Conduct	Commitment	Perception	
Overall	.557* (0.000)	.583* (0.000)	.158* (0.006)	.597* (0.000)

Each indicator of the independent variable, socialization when correlated with all the indicators of the dependent variable, teacher professionalism obtained overall r- value ranging from 0.158 to 0.583. This means that there is positive correlation between socialization and professionalism of public teachers.

The professionalism of public teachers was found to have a favorable and substantial link with socialization. The study's findings do corroborate those of Gökçe (2020), who found that teachers acquired their skills through socializing and that they were able to stay in the field through collaboration and communication with other educators as well as career-specific situational adjustment.

Table 6: The Influence of Metacognitive Awareness and Socialization on Teacher Professionalism

Independent Variables	Teacher Professionalism (Dependent Variables)			
	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	1.301	.136	9.577	.000
Metacognitive Awareness (MA)	.690	.563	11.925	.000
Socialization (SOC)	.078	.059	1.346	.179
R	.751			
R ²	.564			
F	193.769			
p	.000			

Moreover, the outcomes are consistent with Obudaro's (2018) research, which found that socialization helped instructors develop their professionalism. The study's research findings align with the conclusions of Qadeer's (2020) study, which posited that mentorship roles played by instructors may play a significant influence in facilitating professional development. They were therefore able to define their job and create a professional identity, encompassing knowledge, skills, norms, and values, thanks to competent interactions between professors and colleagues as well as mentoring (Salisu et al., 2019).

Shown in Table 6 are the results of test on the significant relationship between the variables such as metacognitive awareness, socialization and professionalism. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between the variables as the overall p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05. The R2 of 0.564 had shown that only 56.4% of the variability of the teacher professionalism was due to the variability of the metacognitive awareness and socialization. The remaining 53.6 % variation could be attributed to the variables that were not covered in the study. The analysis had shown that when metacognitive awareness was regressed on teacher professionalism, it produced an overall p-value of 0.000. Whereas, socialization was regressed on teacher professionalism, it produced an overall p-value of 0.179. Thus, the p value of metacognitive awareness was lesser than 0.05, whereas the p value of socialization was greater than 0.05. Therefore, metacognitive awareness significantly influences the professionalism of the public teachers, however socialization does not significantly influence the professionalism of the public teachers.

The relationship between socialization and metacognitive awareness justifies identifying the variables that have a major impact on public educators' professionalism. Regression analysis revealed that one potential predictor of the effect on public teachers' professionalism may be metacognitive awareness. It also becomes clear that socialization cannot be used to anticipate how public teachers' professionalism would be affected.

It is suggested that by concentrating on determining metacognitive awareness, it may have an impact on teachers' professional development. The study's conclusions support the claim made by Mbato and Triprihatmini (2022) that teachers' professional development was aided by their metacognitive awareness. Furthermore, through metacognitive awareness, instructors can improve their professionalism by using 21st century basic thinking skills to support them with teaching, strategy selection, and cultivating a positive view of their work (Cengelci&Egmir, 2022).

Furthermore, learning and teaching metacognitively resulted in high academic achievement levels for both students and teachers (Darmawan, Zubaidah, Ristanto, Zamzami, & Wahono, 2020). Therefore, Nielsen (2019) reaffirmed that the metacognitive person engaged in active learning, had the ability to study on their own, used a variety of approaches to address difficulties, and pursued further education for career advancement.

Conversely, it is claimed that the socialization process cannot potentially have an impact on the professional growth of teachers. It also contradicts the findings of Darmawan et al. (2020), who found that informal contact with close colleagues provided the context for support and

positively impacted teacher integration and professional growth.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

The general level of metacognitive awareness, which resulted from highly developed declarative, procedural, conditional, and regulatory knowledge of cognition, including information, planning, monitoring, debugging techniques, and evaluation. This indicates that educators frequently exhibit the following knowledge.

Furthermore, knowledge of cognition as it relates to procedural knowledge, regulation of cognition as it relates to monitoring, and evaluation scored lowest among all the indicators' high mean score levels. In order to assess their demands in their line of work, teachers must constantly be aware of their cognitive abilities and their grasp of the aforementioned information.

Likewise, it is crucial to highlight the role that the previously described knowledge plays in the learning processes that could potentially contribute to the development of components that provide comprehensive metacognitive awareness inside the framework of professional development. Additionally, trainings, programs, and attaining professional advancement are beneficial in that they enrich knowledge by acquiring new information regarding the evolving educational landscape. It is also advised that teachers update their professional skills in order to stay up to date with the modifications, learning objectives, and scholarly trends of the new curriculum.

Besides, the degree of socialization resulted from exceptionally high levels of job, group, and organization socialization. This indicates that teachers always exhibited socialization in the course of their work. Regression analysis results, however, showed that socialization had a substantial relationship with professional identity but had no effect on public teachers' professionalism. Furthermore, organization socialization had the lowest mean score among all the indications of socialization, despite their extremely high levels. As a result, they must constantly look for methods to interact and work together with their coworkers on concepts, practical plans, and methods that will advance their careers.

Furthermore, the high standards of devotion, perception, and code of conduct contributed to the professionalism of teachers. This indicates that public secondary teachers always observe professionalism. Perception also had the lowest ranking among the indicators. Therefore, in order for teachers to progress professionally, they must be encouraged to take part in numerous trainings and programs or even pursue a professional next-level degree.

Moreover, this research presented that variable such as metacognitive awareness may have an impact on a teacher's professionalism. However, variable such as socialization are unlikely to have an impact on a teacher's professionalism. The aforementioned results also demonstrated that professional teachers were seen to be content with their

work, to apply suitable values and beliefs to their career, and to have a good outlook on teaching and learning.

Furthermore, future researchers may take into consideration for further studies in order to arrive at more precise conclusions about the ways in which socialization and metacognitive awareness affect the professionalism of public secondary teachers. In light of this, it is advised that school administrators support teachers in their efforts to advance academically and professionally by encouraging them to participate in a variety of seminars, training courses, and graduate-level coursework. This helps teachers and students become more metacognitive aware of their own learning, which in turn promotes academic growth.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study's findings indicate that public teachers have a high degree of metacognitive awareness across all domains, including knowledge of cognition (declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge) and regulation of cognition (planning, information management, monitoring, debugging techniques, and evaluation). Furthermore, knowledge of cognition as it relates to procedural knowledge, regulation of cognition as it relates to monitoring, and evaluation scored lowest among the high levels of mean scores of all the indicators.

Additionally, the study found that public teachers had extremely high levels of socialization across all indicators, including task, group, and organization socialization. However, it was discovered that instructors' professionalism was found to be high, with extremely high ratings for dedication, middling ratings for perception, and extremely high ratings for code of conduct. Furthermore, the study indicates a substantial relationship and correlation between instructors' professionalism and their metacognitive awareness. It also reveals a connected relationship between teachers' professionalism and socialization. It does, however, demonstrate that socialization exerts little influence on public educators' professionalism.

The findings are consistent with Kohlberg's theory of moral development, which holds that educators make metacognitive decisions about their professional lives. As a result, the findings support the hypothesis put forth by Gaikhorst, Beishuizen, Korstjens, and Volman (2018) that there is a correlated but non-significant relationship between socialization and teacher professionalism. The study also claimed that a lack of adequate mentoring and support contributed to academic abandonment. Furthermore, the findings supported the structural functionalism theory put forth by Kingsbury and Scanzoni, which held that when school personnel showed a professional interest in students and helped them with challenges they faced in their careers, success in the classroom was a team effort (Alhija&Fresco, 2020).

It is clear from the positive association and substantial influence that metacognitive awareness has an impact on the advancement of public teachers' professionalism. Additionally, while analyzing the socialization data, it was shown that while there is a positive association, socializing

has no discernible impact on the professionalism of public teachers. This suggests that socialization has little bearing on the advancement of teacher professionalism.

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